

A need for routine regular vertical profiling in the Arctic atmosphere

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A robust evaluation of how meteorology, trace gases, and aerosols vary with altitude in the atmosphere is critical for understanding the rapidly changing Arctic. This information is needed to assess anthropogenic and natural source influences on Arctic clouds and climate forcing, understand surface-atmosphere coupling, constrain Arctic numerical weather prediction, and to inform model process development. However, there is a severe lack of regular vertical profiling in this region, particularly outside of summer and over the central and eastern Arctic. The Arctic RISE (Arctic Routine atmoSpheric profile sampling) initiative aims to improve coverage of Arctic vertical profile measurements, to address this challenge.

Models that integrate our understanding of Arctic physical, chemical and biogeochemical systems require sufficient observational data for constraint of their processes and initial state, and for evaluation. Numerical weather prediction is reliant on accurate initial conditions, and a severe lack of observations throughout the Arctic vertical profile degrades the quality of, for example, extreme Arctic weather. Even for temperature, observations are essentially missing for much of the high Arctic lower troposphere profile. Earth system models include parameterisations for small-scale and complex processes, which require observations to underpin process-level understanding and build relationships between simulated parameters. Prediction of how Arctic temperatures will respond to changes in aerosol and radiatively active trace gas emissions transported from lower latitudes and from the Arctic itself requires models that are able to accurately simulate response of atmospheric trace gas and aerosol distributions to emission changes. For constituents such as ozone and black carbon aerosol, their atmospheric radiative effects are sensitive to their vertical distribution (Flanner et al., 2013, Rap et al., 2015), meaning that assessment of model-simulated profiles in the Arctic is crucial. Model-simulated trace gas and aerosol profiles are highly diverse in the Arctic with large inter-model variability (Samset et al., 2013; Whaley et al., 2022). The observational constraint needed to diagnose model accuracy and to deduce drivers of model diversity is lacking.

Regular in-situ measurements of vertical distributions of temperature, humidity, together with key trace gas and aerosol parameters in the Arctic would be transformative for constraint of models and process understanding, particularly outside of summer. Moreover, both improvements in high latitude satellite retrievals and their validation with additional in-situ profile measurements would greatly enhance observational coverage. We argue that there is a critical need for a step-change in both the spatial coverage and frequency of Arctic atmosphere vertical profile measurements. The forthcoming International Polar Year (IPY) 2032-33 offers a timely and unique opportunity to build and coordinate international community action to achieve this.

Implementation of routine Arctic vertical profiling

Arctic RISE aims to develop and implement a network of widespread, coordinated, sustained, regular vertical profile measurements across the Arctic, across seasons. Development of Arctic RISE has been initiated through a series of workshops and discussions led by the PACES (air Pollution in the Arctic: Climate Environment and Societies) initiative, coordinated under IGBP IGAC and the International Arctic Science Committee. It will capitalize on recent advances in measurement techniques including automated sampling and miniaturization. The goal is to transform capabilities for measuring regular Arctic vertical profiles, to coordinate data collection and sharing, and to feed collected measurements into operational centres, Earth system model evaluation and development, and Arctic scientific assessments.

Figure 1: Arctic RISE multi-component measurement approach, and links to scientific, operational and policy-facing agencies.

Arctic RISE will be built around a multi-component approach, acting as an overarching umbrella for coordination of activities across different platforms (Fig. 1), and ensuring longevity of the overall network. This will help to manage the potential for temporally and spatially disjointed funding for individual components, and facilitate links with international scientific and governance agencies to ensure optimal exploitation of new datasets. In collaboration with existing Arctic observing infrastructure and agencies, this initiative will lead to coordination of data collection, curation and hosting across multiple new and existing in-situ and remote-sensed Arctic vertical measurements. Importantly, Arctic RISE also aims to coordinate standardisation, evaluation and assessments of interoperability for measurements. It will foster new research and development opportunities for small sensor and autonomous measurement technologies aligned to deployments of instrumentation on a range of sampling platforms in the Arctic.

The network seeks to bring together measurements from a variety of in-situ platforms, including aircraft, uncrewed aerial vehicles, tethered platforms such as helikites (Pohorsky et al., 2025), as well as linking to on-going ground-based networks of in-situ and ground-based remote sensing measurements and high-latitude satellite profile measurements. Opportunities for community-led measurement initiatives will also be an integral part of the proposed structure. This ambitious programme aims to deliver a transformative enhancement in the coverage of regular vertical sampling across the Arctic region. The IPY 2032-33 will be a focus to bring together this large increase in measurement activity, and to develop coordination with modelling centres and assessment programmes, and to demonstrate the value of the proposed network. The ambition is that this will leave a legacy of ongoing coordinated measurement activity over the following years and decades.

To register interest in Arctic RISE and future planned workshops, and for opportunities to help develop the initiative, please visit: <https://tinyurl.com/3ubcprmv>.

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